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“WANDERING EMMA”

An endearing woman in her late thirties, Emma is now very desperate to find love before getting forty. She had devoted herself at her job for seventeen years and she figured, she had better devote her life for herself now, before everything gets too late. So, in search for love, Emma decided to spend the money she saved up to give herself a tour around the world in search for the love of her life.

First, she went to one of the most charming places in the world, Paris. She wandered around the place but found no romantic love there, instead she found love for Paris’ culture and language. For the length of her stay there, she spent so much time studying French and embracing the fullness of Paris’ culture. After going to Paris, she then went to Italy, where she learned to love art and cuisine. While staying there, she also devoted herself in studying Italian so as to genuinely communicate with the Italian people. Her next stop was Prague which made her fall in love with the Bohemian culture. Then Budapest, the capital of Hungary, helped her fall in love with giving value to social etiquette, and personal space. Truly, in Budapest, she had so much time learning to love herself too.

After travelling around almost all of the most beautiful places in Europe, she then decided to explore the continent of her origin, Asia. Surely, there are so many places to go and explore in Asia. Her first stop was in Bali, Indonesia, where she fell in love with nature more like any other work of art. She spent most of her time exploring beaches, and going hiking to mountains. These activities also kept her at peace, and gave her the feeling of contentment in solitude. After Bali, she then went to the Maldives to explore the beaches there. This place taught her to be carefree, and kind altogether. After the Maldives, she decided, she had to explore South Korea, hoping she’d find her own romance there. But she rather fell in love with South Korea’s most beautiful sceneries. Some of the sceneries she went to were in Nami and Jeju Island. She also found South Korea’s culture and language an endearing one. She was so amazed to know that Korean young people give so much respect to the elders. They even have the so-called honorifics in their language to specially address elders and show respect to them. After exploring Korea, she went to Japan. If South Koreans were respectful, Japanese are very respectful too! She learned how the Japanese people value work and order. The Japanese language also suited her liking, so, while was there, she also spent an ample time studying Hiragana, Katakana, and Kanji.

Although Europe and Asia did not give her the love of her life, the places that she went to in those continents made her fall in love with their rich culture and loveable languages. She even forgets the reason why she went there!

The last place on Emma’s travel list is Africa. She went around this vast continent. Among the countries she visited were Zambia, Sierra Leone, Democratic Republic of Congo, and Ethiopia. Emma was amazed at how different each country is when it comes to their culture, although they have some similar cultures too. But what made Emma fall in love with this country is the people themselves. Emma found genuine innocence in them. Although she found it hard

to communicate to them due to Africa's diverse language, she used her heart to communicate to them. She showed the African people her love for their culture and embraced it like it was her own. The language barrier did not even feel like a barrier at all because she exerted so much effort in showing the African people her love. After exploring Africa, she then decided to go home.

On her way to Manila, Emma had so much time internalizing everything that she learned from the many places she went to. Her trip helped her learn to communicate to people through their language and culture but more so, she learned to connect to them by heart. Indeed, language and culture go hand in hand in helping people understand, express, and communicate. Although she failed to find romantic love in all of her trips, the love that she found is counted more than that of romance. She finally learned to love herself and the people around her, which she believes to be the greatest love of all.

